

D2.4

IMPROVED GHG MONITORING PRACTICES - ENVIRONMENTAL INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT OF LMTs IN CASE STUDIES

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Based on the concept of environmental integrity this report identifies general requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms. It identifies potential risks for environmental integrity but also opportunities for integrating land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) into international and national climate policies. These requirements are discussed for different types of LMTs. The requirements are transformed into a protocol for assessing risks for environmental integrity associated with specific LMTs in the format of a survey. The survey can be used for informing LMT practitioners and investors on the marketability of mitigation outcomes of LMT implementation. The results of the completion of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case study leaders is used to highlight potential risks for environmental integrity but also opportunities for integrating LMT solutions into international and national climate policies. A synthesis provides conclusions and recommendations for specific stakeholder groups, including LMT practitioners (e.g., farmers, forest managers) and policy makers.	
Evidence of accomplishment	
This report.	

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors,
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions.
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs,

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia, and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Executive summary

This report¹ provides guidance and support to LMT practitioners (main target group) and other readers (LMT investors, farmers, forest managers, local communities, policy makers, etc.) in three ways:

1. Introduction and thematic background on challenges of integrating LMTs into climate policy instruments, with a special focus on carbon market mechanisms,
2. Elaboration of specific risks for environmental integrity of LMTs including description of risk, challenges and approaches for risk mitigation (literature review and review of existing market mechanisms),
3. Presentation of a protocol for assessing environmental integrity and marketability in the format of a survey addressing case study leads and an analysis of results of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case studies.

The report identifies environmental integrity as a comprehensive concept that is widely used for assessing market mechanisms for climate change mitigation. Environmental integrity as defined in the deliverable includes but also goes beyond monitoring of GHGs. The deliverable discusses main challenges regarding environmental integrity that are related to:

- ensuring permanence of emission reductions or carbon removals,
- the demonstration of additionality of mitigation activities,
- establishing credible baselines,
- addressing the risk of leakage from shifting of activities,
- quantifying net carbon storage with effective monitoring systems,
- avoiding double counting, and
- establishing safeguards to reduce negative impacts and generate co-benefits.

Based on the concept of environmental integrity the report identifies general requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms. These requirements are discussed for different types of LMTs. A review of approaches for addressing challenges including 16 different programs and standards provides insights into how environmental integrity risks can be avoided, mitigated and addressed.

The requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms are transformed into a protocol for assessing risks for environmental integrity associated with specific LMTs in the format of a survey. The survey can be used to inform LMT practitioners, farmers, forest owners/managers, investors on the marketability of mitigation outcomes of LMT implementation. The results of the completion of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case studies is used to highlight potential risks for environmental integrity but also opportunities for integrating LMT solutions into international and national climate policies. A synthesis provides conclusions for LMT practitioners and policy makers.

¹ Deliverable D2.4 of the LANDMARC project, presenting results of Task 2.4

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The role of the land-use sector for climate change mitigation becomes more important, as more and more countries, companies and institutions are pledging to achieve net-zero GHG targets and envisage that removals, including those from the land-use sector, provide negative emission contributions for achieving these targets. The Kyoto Protocol already allowed countries to receive credits for carbon sequestration through land-based activities including afforestation, reforestation, improved forestry, improved agricultural practices, and revegetation. However, the land-use sector in many regions, forms the basis for multiple ecosystem services and is therefore subject to different, often opposing policy regimes.

Overview studies see considerable low-cost potential for land-use activities that can potentially bring also high levels of sustainable development and other benefits (Griscom et al. 2017; Roe et al. 2021). A major challenge constitutes to direct funding streams towards the realisation of such mitigation potentials while still allowing for the provision of other ecosystem services from land use. **Carbon markets and other market mechanisms** are considered an additional funding source that can lead to a reduction of GHG emissions and an increase in carbon storage in the land use sector. Carbon markets are trading systems in which carbon credits are sold and bought. Tradable carbon credits in these markets can be attributed to an equivalent tonne of carbon dioxide reduced, sequestered, or avoided. Funding comes from market actors that want to compensate for emissions or achieve other sustainability targets. The Kyoto protocol set up the **Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)** as a carbon offset scheme to allow countries to fund mitigation projects in other countries and claim reduced emissions under their emissions targets.

Opportunities and challenges of an integration of land-use activities into market mechanisms as an instrument have been the subject of controversial discussion for decades (Caparrós and Jacquemont 2003; Barua et al. 2014). In general, land-use activities bear a risk of negative impacts on people, nature, and climate. More specific challenges related carbon markets include ensuring **permanence** of emission reductions or carbon removals, the demonstration of **additionality** of mitigation activities, establishing credible **baselines**, addressing the risk of **leakage** from shifting of activities, **quantifying** net carbon storage with effective **monitoring systems**, avoiding **double counting**, and establishing **safeguards** to reduce negative impacts and generate **co-benefits**.

There is also the risk that large supply of credits at very low prices could delay climate action and innovation in other sectors. If within a compliance system, fossil fuel emission reduction obligations are compensated with land-use activities more carbon from stable geological reservoirs is being transferred into instable pools in the biosphere that are more easily subject to natural disturbances and other forms of reversals.

Due to such concerns, under the Kyoto Protocol's CDM, only afforestation and reforestation projects were allowed (Thomas et al. 2010). In fact, only a few forest projects were implemented under the CDM. One reason for this is because the Kyoto Protocol made buyer countries liable to compensate for any non-permanence: the credits either had a limited validity or had to be replaced by the buyer country in case of non-permanence (Thomas et al. 2010).

The Paris Agreement addressed the opportunity for voluntary cooperation among countries and market mechanisms to allow for higher ambition under its Article 6. This Article sets out principles for such cooperations involving international trade including principles for **environmental integrity, transparency, and robust accounting**. Neither Article 6 nor the decisions on rules for Article 6 include a specific reference to the land-use sector. The decisions include, however, references to addressing non-permanence, which can be interpreted such that activities with non-permanence risks are eligible under Article 6, if non-permanence risks are appropriately addressed.

The inclusion of land-use activities was also controversially discussed in the negotiations on the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) adopted under the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). Technical Advisory Body (TAB) finally recommended to include emission reduction units from land use to be eligible under CORSIA including avoided deforestation (ICAO 2020). There was criticism that the criteria for the inclusion do not ensure environmental integrity (Broekhoff et al. 2020).

In addition, several governmental and non-governmental carbon crediting mechanisms have permitted the registration of land-use activities. Examples include the American Carbon Registry (ACR), Architecture for REDD+ transactions/The REDD Environmental Excellency Standard (ART TREES), the Australia Emission Reduction Fund, California Tropical Forest Standard, Climate Action Reserve, Verra's Jurisdictional and Nested REDD+ (JNR) and its Verified Carbon Standard (VCS), and the UK Peatland Code and Woodland Carbon Code. Verra's VCS Program holds the largest share of land use projects². It permits projects (under the Verified Carbon Standard³, VCS) and sectoral approaches (under the Jurisdictional and Nested REDD+⁴, JNR). Other carbon crediting mechanisms have specialised in the land-use sector (e.g., Plan Vivo, UK Woodland Carbon Code, Moor futures). With the Forest Carbon Partnership Facility⁵ (FCPF), the World Bank has launched its own programme for the use of market approaches in the forest sector and the BioCarbon Fund for the wider land-use sector.

These carbon crediting mechanisms have so far mainly been used in the **voluntary market**, i.e., by buyers which offset their emissions voluntarily, offer carbon neutral products or services, achieve climate neutrality or net-zero targets, or simply finance emission reductions elsewhere. Some governments also recognise these standards under national climate policies. In Colombia, for example, companies can use credits from certain standards to meet a **CO₂-tax** (Gobierno de Colombia 2015). In addition, several of these standards have been approved under CORSIA.

In the EU's current common agricultural policy (CAP) for 2023-2027, the concept of **eco-schemes** was introduced. They are an instrument designed to reward farmers for climate action. It delivers yearly direct payments for voluntarily adopted biodiversity and climate-friendly farming practices with higher environmental benefits. Member States are free to choose eco-scheme measures through their CAP Strategic Plans (CSP). Eco-schemes are one instrument that EU Member States can use to reduce land use emissions and increase natural sinks to achieve nationally binding net GHG targets imposed by the (EC) with its Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (**LULUCF Regulation**) (European Commission 2021). It requires Member States to achieve a net zero

² <https://verra.org/programs/verified-carbon-standard/area-of-focus-agriculture-forestry-land-use/>

³ <https://verra.org/programs/verified-carbon-standard/>

⁴ <https://verra.org/programs/jurisdictional-nested-redd-framework/>

⁵ <https://www.forestcarbonpartnership.org/>

target for the LULUCF sector in the period 2021-2025 applying specific accounting rules and a total EU net removal target of -310 Mt CO₂ in 2030 that is allocated to national binding removal targets at Member State level (Böttcher et al. 2022a).

In December 2022, the European Commission (EC) published a proposal for a **Carbon Removal Certification Framework** (CRCF, EC 2022). The CRCF regulation aims to set out how carbon removals will be certified, monitored, and accounted for in the EU. It provides a framework to approve future carbon removal certification schemes in the EU. It addresses removals that result in permanent geological storage, as well as temporary removals in biomass, soils, and products. The framework applies to voluntary carbon markets in EU and provides an EU certificate for voluntarily traded removal units.

In summary, finance opportunities for land-based mitigation techniques and practices (LMTs) are on the rise. However, with the growing number of instruments, there is also the increasing need for guiding information for both, the demand side of investors and buyers and the supply side of landowners, farmers, and foresters. There is also an increasing need to ensure that the individual climate incentive schemes and their associated GHG accounting systems are properly aligned (see also the following LANDMARC report, D2.5 'Guidance report for potential role of carbon offsetting schemes and Paris Agreement').

1.2. Aim of the deliverable

This report provides guidance and support to case study leads (main target group) and other readers (LANDMARC stakeholders, policy makers, etc.) in three ways:

1. Introduction and thematic background on challenges of integrating LMTs into climate policy instruments, with a special focus on carbon market mechanisms,
2. Elaboration of specific risks for environmental integrity of LMTs including description of risk, challenges and approaches for risk mitigation (literature review and review of existing market mechanisms),
3. Presentation of a protocol for assessing environmental integrity and marketability in the format of a survey addressing case study leads and an analysis of results of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case studies.

Based on the concept of environmental integrity the report identifies general requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms. These requirements are discussed for different types of LMTs. A review of approaches for addressing challenges including 16 different programs and standards provides insights into how environmental integrity risks can be avoided, mitigated, and addressed.

The requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms are transformed into a protocol for assessing risks for environmental integrity associated with specific LMTs in the format of a survey. The survey is used for informing case study leads on the marketability of mitigation outcomes of LMT implementation. The results of the completion of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case studies is used to highlight potential risks for environmental integrity but also opportunities for integrating LMT solutions into international and national climate policies. A synthesis provides conclusions for LMT practitioners, investors, and policy makers.

The report includes the developed protocol for assessing risks for environmental integrity associated with specific LMTs (see Annex 2) that provides guidance on which market mechanisms can potentially be targeted for marketing of mitigation outcomes.

2. Methodology

2.1. Definition of environmental integrity

‘**Environmental integrity**’ is a concept to assess environmental damage and often referred to for describing an undisturbed state of natural conditions, accounting also for dynamics that natural ecosystems are underlying. The objective of environmental integrity is thus to sustain important biophysical processes that provide ecosystem services and to protect the resilience, diversity, and intactness of ecosystems. In the context of climate policy under the UNFCCC, the Paris Agreement defines the term as ‘integrity of all ecosystems, including oceans, and the protection of biodiversity, recognized by some cultures as Mother Earth [...]’⁶. Environmental integrity was also introduced already in the Marrakesh Accords⁷ supplementing the Kyoto protocol. The principles in the Marrakesh Accords responded to concerns that the use of land-based mitigation activities undermine emission reduction obligations of the Kyoto Protocol. They required a solid scientific basis, consistent methodologies over time, that ‘the mere presence of carbon stocks be excluded from accounting’, that activities contribute to the conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of natural resources, and that reversal of any removal due to land-based mitigation activities ‘be accounted for at the appropriate point in time’.

In the scientific literature on climate policy the term ‘environmental integrity’ also constitutes a threshold for the effectiveness of mitigation measures that need to lead to an overall decrease in global aggregate emissions (e.g., Schneider and La Hoz Theuer 2019). Applying this definition to carbon market mechanisms implies that ‘environmental integrity’ is ensured if crediting and trade of mitigation outcomes of activities lead to aggregated global GHG emissions lower than in situation where crediting and transfer did not take place.

In this deliverable we apply a definition of ‘environmental integrity’ that goes beyond GHG monitoring and accounting aspects. We assume that environmental integrity is ensured if the following challenges to the integration of land use activities into market mechanisms have been successfully addressed and resolved:

- demonstrating **additionality** of mitigation activities,
- establishing credible **baselines**,
- addressing the **risk of leakage** from shifting of activities,
- quantifying net carbon storage with effective **monitoring systems**,
- avoiding **double counting** both between national targets and when integrating activities into other accounting frameworks, and
- addressing the potential **non-permanence** of stored carbon.
- Moreover, the land-use sector forms the basis for multiple ecosystem services. Therefore, key considerations to find the necessary political support for the integration of the land-use sector are establishing **environmental and social safeguards** to minimize trade-offs and considering co-benefits in decision making.

⁶ <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/2015/cop21/eng/l09r01.pdf>

⁷ https://unfccc.int/cop7/documents/accords_draft.pdf

In the following, we are elaborating on these aspects as potential indicators for assessing ‘environmental integrity’ of the integration of specific land-based mitigation activities into carbon market mechanisms. The analysis builds on a recently published analysis of 16 different standards market mechanisms (Böttcher et al. 2022b).

2.2. Approaches for ensuring environmental integrity of LMT implementation

2.2.1. *Baselines*

Baselines describe the level of emissions or removals prior to an activity that leads to emission reduction or removals. Emissions or removals occurring after the implementation of an activity are compared to the baseline to measure success or failure of the activity. The term baseline describes the underlying scenario that would occur in the absence of any activity and the associated emission or removal levels. To provide an example: for assessing the result of an activity to bring down emissions occurring from deforestation in an area, a scenario of continued deforestation at historic rates could form a baseline, e.g., representing business-as-usual levels. Baselines can be used in crediting mechanisms for demonstrating additionality (see below). The term reference-level is also commonly used in the land-use sector instead of baseline.

The general challenge with baselines, as reference for describing the situation without project implementation, is that it constitutes a counterfactual scenario. Such a scenario cannot be observed but only estimated, in general with very high uncertainties. Estimates may even have uncertainties higher than expected emission reductions or removals, indicating a clear issue of ‘signal-to-noise-ratio’ (Schneider et al. 2014). Uncertainties vary with the type of LMT. High uncertainties are associated with baselines related to LMTs aiming at emission reductions through reducing deforestation or forest degradation. In comparison, baselines for crediting afforestation and reforestation are typically less uncertain. If baseline emissions are overestimated or removals are underestimated environmental integrity is undermined (Böttcher et al. 2022b). Underestimation of baseline emission might instead reduce attractiveness of LMTs implementation and diminish potential funding.

There are several approaches that can be used to determine baselines. It is important to consider the scope of the LMT at which it will be implemented, e.g., at project level, regional, or entire country. There are typically the following approaches referred to Four main approaches are introduced here (Böttcher et al. 2022b). It is important to consider the scope of the LMT at which it will be implemented, e.g., at project level, regional, or entire country. There are typically the following approaches referred to:

- **Reference area:** A similar area with no activity implementation is compared to the project area. The emission reduction or removals are determined in retrospect, based on the comparison with the reference area. This approach is suitable for rather small-scale activities.
- **(Adjusted) historical average:** This approach simply assumes that the situation of a defined period in the past years will also be the situation of the future and so will also the related emissions or removal levels. The approach can be adjusted to consider specific circumstances. This approach is suitable at the project and jurisdictional level.
- **Historical trend:** This variant of the (adjusted) historical average approach can be used where a trend in past historical data is noted, such as a decrease in deforestation. The trend of the past is extrapolated

to the future and so are associated emissions or removal levels. This approach is suitable at the project and jurisdictional level.

- **Modelling:** A modelling approach is the most challenging, as scenario analysis involves complex projections under which the integration of different drivers, future policies, and planned measures are possible. Baselines based on model projections can quickly be outdated as drivers and underlying data might change. Regular updates are therefore important. This approach is typically used for jurisdiction and national level crediting.

Independent of how baselines are derived, they always represent a future emissions and removals level. Baselines are thus projections that anticipate a future development of land-use change, e.g., by interpreting drivers of past trends or making assumptions on a business-as-usual development. The approaches differ in which scenario is assumed for the future and which data basis is used to estimate emissions or removals associated with the baseline scenario.

Regarding uncertainty of baselines and the obtainment of ‘environmental integrity’, many carbon crediting mechanisms apply the ‘**principle of conservativeness**’, meaning that the baselines must be estimated conservatively, and emissions or removals should be defined with a bias toward underestimation.

2.2.2. *Additionality*

A common definition of additionality assumes that additionality is given when emission reductions or removals occur because of the incentives created by carbon crediting revenues. An assessment of additionality is important because it demonstrates that the crediting mechanism forms the decisive factor of the implementation of an LMT. Additionality is better assured when a single measure is implemented, and the observed results can be clearly attributed to that measure. Determining causality between an LMT and emission reductions and removals is challenging because land-use emissions and removals are impacted by multiple direct and indirect social and economic drivers. Creating a clear correlation between the implemented LMT and the achieved emission reduction and removals proves almost impossible for LMTs related to reducing emissions from deforestation and degradation (Cames et al. 2017; Trexler 2019; Schneider 2009). For other LMTs additionality can be assessed easier, e.g., for afforestation and reforestation or wetland restoration as they are probably not additional if they generate income from harvesting biomass, respectively probably are additional if they do not generate income other than from carbon credits and if they are not incentivized through other policies and regulations (Böttcher et al. 2022b).

Additionality is the most important aspect regarding ensuring the quality of carbon credits (Gillenwater 2012; Michaelowa, Axel, Shishlov, Igor et al. 2019). There are three common approaches to determine additionality:

- **Activity-specific, stepwise additionality assessments:** The carbon crediting mechanism assesses additionality for an activity based on a stepwise approach aiming to identify activities that would also be implemented in the absence of a carbon crediting mechanism. The first step does a **regulatory analysis** and is also used to identify the most likely alternative scenario to the project which then is taken as the baseline. The second step comprises an **investment analysis** to assess the financial viability of an activity. The activity is not additional if the analysis shows that the mitigation activity is financially the most feasible option

without carbon credit revenues. The third step is a **barrier analysis** to identify hurdles that might occur even though the activity is considered as financially profitable, such as political, institutional, social barriers.

- **Standardized additionality assessments:** The standardized additionality assessment aims at delivering more objective results on additionality of an activity (Broekhoff 2007) and tries excluding subjective judgements needed under the activity-stepwise assessment. The assessment makes use of ‘eligibility criteria’ which define the type of mitigation activity that is eligible for crediting.
- **Additionality assessment through comparison to a jurisdictional baseline:** This approach is commonly used within the land-use sector and allows to compare the emissions of an entire jurisdiction to a **baseline emission level** for that jurisdiction. The approach is an alternative to crediting at the individual project level and allows to combine multiple measures and policy interventions to reduce emissions. Additionality under the jurisdictional approach is mostly considered as achieved if emissions in the project area are reduced below the baseline of the jurisdiction.

Elements of the first two approaches are often combined at carbon crediting mechanisms.

2.2.3. *Non-permanence*

LMTs that reduce emissions or remove carbon are susceptible to being reversed at a later point in time as carbon stocks could be lost through natural or human-induced disturbances. The risk of non-permanence is associated with the type of carbon pools. The likeliness that a specific carbon pool is reversed is very much depending on the underlying processes how carbon is stored, and in which form it is fixed. Biomass pools have a higher turnover in comparison to soil carbon pools and thus carbon can be released faster.

It is crucial to address the issue of non-permanence as this affects the environmental integrity of a crediting mechanism. Reversal of emission reductions or removals might lead to a net increase in global emissions, if, due to an issuance of credits at an earlier point of time based on observed mitigation (Schneider and La Hoz Theuer 2019).

Non-permanence is a risk that applies to all LMTs. Avoided deforestation and degradation as a mitigation measure must be sustained in perpetuity to avoid falling back to baseline levels. Similarly, afforestation and reforestation activities can be followed by reversal of stored carbon if natural or human-caused drivers of reservoir depletion are not adequately addressed (e.g., through adaptation measures to increase ecosystem resilience). This leads to the conclusion that emissions avoidance is better for environmental integrity than carbon removal with a significant risk of non-permanence.

Addressing non-permanence is challenging as there are no clear specifications on how long the period must be under which reversal risk should be considered. Some crediting mechanisms require the monitoring of permanence over time horizons of up to 100 years. From a mitigation perspective, released CO₂ increases atmospheric concentration for thousands of years as CO₂ requiring that reservoirs are keeping it in a similar order of magnitude. Approaches of crediting mechanisms identifying and compensating for reversals are needed to ensure environmental integrity of emission reductions and removals (Fearnside 2002; Murray et al. 2012). The following four approaches are in use by carbon crediting mechanisms (Böttcher et al. 2022b):

- **Reducing non-permanence risks:** This approach is based on results of a non-permanence risk assessment which then leads to the exclusion of mitigation activities with high risks from eligibility or provisions to mitigate reversal risks.
- **Monitoring and compensation for reversals:** This approach emphasizes compensation for reversals through cancellation of issued carbon credits. Doing so implies constant monitoring to detect reversals and the scope of it. There are several designs that focus on different aspects such as time horizon, reversals in case of irregular monitoring or discontinuation, reversals after regular ending of monitoring, updating of baselines, and responsibilities for compensating of reversals.
- **Issuing temporary carbon credits:** The CDM AR carbon crediting mechanism considers carbon storage as a 'rented' mitigation result that is temporal. Temporary credits are issued that expire after a defined period. After the expiration credits are replaced by permanent units without the consideration whether non-permanence has occurred or not (Maréchal and Hecq 2006; Marland and Marland 2009).
- **Discounting:** This approach allows discounts on emission reductions or removals to address the risks of non-permanence. A share of the reductions or removals are not issued as carbon credits. Discounting is simple to implement as there is no requirement to assign liability for reversals, certainty to activity supporter is created, and their risks are reduced as no action is required when a reversal occurs. In terms of environmental integrity, discounting is problematic because it provides limited incentives for activity proponents to avoid reversals and thus creates moral hazard problems. Moreover, given the lack of incentives to avoid reversals discount rates may need to be set quite high to be on the safe side that non-permanence is addressed.

2.2.4. *Leakage risks*

Activities for reducing emissions or increasing removals in the land-use sector can affect emissions and removals in other sectors or outside the target area. Such displacements can be caused by activities implemented at different scales, including projects, regional or national scale. While displacement within the system boundaries is usually reflected in the activity's monitored emissions, leakage is a displacement happening outside the boundaries of the activity (Henders and Ostwald 2012). Three different types of leakages are typically differentiated (Böttcher et al. 2022b):

- **Direct leakage:** Leakage effects caused by the direct shift in the supply of products or services from one area to another through the implementation of an activity, such as the displacement of grazing land for cows to another area (activity shifting).
- **Indirect leakage:** Leakage effects caused by the implementation of an activity in one area indirectly creating incentives for changes in activities in other areas. Indirect effects are usually caused by the reduction in supply of products or services leading to a shift in markets, such as increased crop production in other areas due to a reduction of crop production on the targeted land area (market effects). Indirect leakage effects can be at local, national, and global level.
- **Ecological leakage:** Leakage effects caused by the implementation of an activity in one area affecting natural processes stretching out to surrounding ecosystems outside an activity's boundary leading to emissions, e.g., if organic soils in an area are rewetted affecting the hydrological properties of ecosystems outside the area causing tree dieback.

Crediting mechanisms require that leakage effects are identified, mitigated to the degree possible, quantified and finally included in determining total emission reductions or removals. Wherever risks of indirect global leakage occur, activities should be excluded from crediting. The risk of leakage depends partly on the type of activity (e.g., wetland restoration leading to ecological leakage) but even more on the activity design, scale and underlying drivers (Böttcher et al. 2022b). Low-risk activities are those to be implemented on abandoned land with no ongoing agricultural use and for cases where the displaced activity is banned on land potentially affected by leakage. This applies more often to afforestation and reforestation activities than activities avoiding GHG emissions that are usually caused by economic activities on the targeted area that need to be reduced or ceased for achieving reductions in GHG emissions.

If leakage cannot be avoided, it needs to be accounted for by estimating leakage emissions in the total emission reductions and removals (Böttcher et al. 2022b). Direct leakage effects are often measured directly, e.g., by creating a reference area surrounding the activity where leakage might occur. Ecological leakage can also be measured directly, e.g., in the case of LMTs regarding wetland management where water levels are measured, or vegetation is assessed. Secondary leakage cannot be measured directly and thus must be estimated making use of other criteria and indicators. Often an economic analysis assesses likely changes in prices and shifts on markets.

2.2.5. *Monitoring*

Carbon crediting standards require a regular quantification for emission reductions or removals of an activity. This process is called monitoring and consists of measuring, reporting and verification (MRV) and provides a choice of methods for monitoring, emphasizing on the baselines and monitoring methodologies. Regular reporting on emission reductions or removals is mandatory and usually verified independently. The estimation of emissions and removals for baselines and the project period relies on good quality data on changes in carbon stocks and area extent. Data on carbon stocks and stock changes can be provided through terrestrial carbon inventories while information on the area can be gained through statistics and remote sensing. The application of models and comparison of scenarios is also possible, especially if the activity area is at a larger geographical scale.

Monitoring of LMTs can often build on existing monitoring systems that were established to document emissions and removals from land use, land-use change and forestry, as established at national level under the UNFCCC (e. g. National Inventory Reports). Moreover, the IPCC (2006) provides guidelines and default factors for monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions and removals by differentiating activity data (often area information) and emission factors (intensity of emission or removal by area unit). However, such reporting systems often lack detailed information to differentiate activities and assess impacts of management changes, required for a robust monitoring and reporting of carbon credits. There are also differences between land use categories and how well GHG emissions and removals are covered. While, e.g., forest monitoring is a rather well-established system in most countries, organic soil management instead requires additional detailed information on site conditions often not readily available. The monitoring of supply chains could build on trade and sales statistics and existing certification and life cycle analyses (LCA).

In the LANDMARC project, research is focused to the development of new methods for the quantification and monitoring of negative emissions using Earth Observation (EO) tools. The approach taken is to combine in-situ

data and EO applications over a wide range of LMTs. The expectations are to improve on accuracy of soil and biomass measurements and advance from Tier 1 (international default values) to Tier 3 methods (country specific values based on modelling or in-situ measurements) to estimate carbon emission reduction or removals. This might also have positive impacts on the quality of future National Inventory Reporting, as this approach may complement current reporting. It captures spatial variability and can be acquired quickly, efficiently, continuously, consistently and in a repeatable way over large areas or areas with difficult access at a cost-effective monitoring. Further, it can also be used for fulfilling the requirements to participate in carbon markets.

2.2.6. *Double counting*

Double counting takes place when a single emission reduction or removal is used more than once to meet mitigation targets (Schneider et al. 2019). The consequence of double counting are higher global emissions, undermining the goal of reducing emissions. When accounting for NDCs and when using approaches under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, Parties are obliged to avert double counting. It is very important to avoid double counting especially in the context of carbon market mechanisms and when different mechanisms are involved at the same time.

Double counting can occur in three main forms that need to be addressed differently:

- **Double issuance** occurs when two units are issued for a single emission reduction or removal. Double issuance can be avoided by either excluding projects that are already registered under a different carbon crediting mechanism or cancel issued carbon credits before reissuing under another mechanism.
- **Double use** occurs if an issued unit is used twice by buyers to achieve mitigation pledges. To avoid double use of carbon credits a clear identification of each credit (serial number) in a registry is necessary. This allows the documentation and tracking of ownership, transfers, and cancellations of issued credits.
- **Double claiming** can occur with domestic mitigation targets and with international mitigation targets and will be addressed with so called 'corresponding adjustment'. This requires countries to adjust their reported emission levels according to their sales and purchases of emission reductions and removals.

2.2.7. *Visibility in GHG inventories*

Crediting mechanisms are instruments that are supposed to support countries with emission reduction and removal obligations to achieve their targets. Therefore, there needs to be visibility of mitigation measures in national GHG reporting. If LMTs are not reflected in national inventories used to assess compliance in the climate policy framework, effects of these measures cannot be accounted towards national targets. This might have implications for the attractiveness of LMTs in carbon markets as an instrument for national policy making.

Inventory visibility can be assessed by identifying which emission sources and gases are affected by a mitigation action, determining the minimum inventory methods required for reflecting the related emission reduction, and identifying the completeness of and methods used by the current GHG inventory (Schneider et al. 2022). In an assessment by Schneider et al. (2022), inventory visibility was found to be generally high for measures that reduce CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion, while especially in the forestry sector there was a higher risk of emission reductions not being visible. Increasing visibility can be achieved by both improving GHG inventories by increasing granularity and the use of emission factors specific for the activities and a separation of areas.

Visibility can be achieved by selecting activities that are already covered by inventory methods. However, a challenge is also the scale at which activities are implemented. Small projects might be invisible due to the small size of the area they affect. The average uncertainties of GHG inventories can easily range between 10 and 500% for some pools and gases (e.g., EU Inventory Report 2022). This implies that even larger improvements in GHG reporting might not be able to change GHG estimates beyond the level of uncertainty. Especially high uncertainties are reported for soil carbon emissions and non-CO₂ gases where processes are less well understood, and data availability is limited.

It is important to note that shortcomings in GHG inventories do not imply that projects operating on areas less well covered by the inventory should be neglected. On the contrary, an increased interest in projects can also help gaining momentum for the processes of inventory compilation. Such processes are often rather slow and of low flexibility. This is because they involve collaboration of different agencies, there is a certain path dependency regarding the data basis and lack of capacities. An example are soil carbon emissions that are underreported in the EU (Bellassen et al. 2022). Projects that operate within such blind spots could contribute to improving the NIR GHG monitoring processes by supplying data for differentiating emission factors and support also the development of more advanced methodologies, including providing ground truth data for modelling.

2.2.8. *Safeguards and co-benefits*

Fearneough et al. (2020) describe safeguards as prerequisites and procedures of carbon crediting mechanisms that target preventing and diminish possible negative impacts. Safeguards can be either social and relate to human rights, gender issues, right of indigenous peoples, etc. or ecological and refer to avert biodiversity loss and keeping environmental quality (Michaelowa, Axel, Shishlov, Igor et al. 2019). Co-benefits always indicate a positive effect beyond the activities purpose. Effected are generally ecosystem system services, e.g., biodiversity increase, and sustainable development goals, such as the generation of income to a local community.

Safeguards are crucial to reduce possible social and environmental risks when LMTs are being implemented under a carbon crediting mechanism. It remains a challenge especially to LMTs in the land use sector where risks need be diminished but cannot be fully prevented.

Co-benefits are important as well because they contribute to the acceptance of an LMT in the land-use sector. In fact, they can in some cases also be considered the main drivers of management change. Deliverable D4.1 of the LANDMARC project found that environmental co-benefits (e.g., water retention, biodiversity gain, etc.) can be the main motivation for farmers and investors to initiate the implementation of an LMT. This is especially true for LMTs with a wide range of co-benefits, e.g., options considered as nature-based solutions. Conceptually, crediting mechanisms are often not able to capture this. This is because a standardization of safeguards and co-benefits is hardly possible as they are very context specific.

The UNFCCC created a list of safeguards that countries, implementing REDD+, need to comply with in a 'systems for providing information on how safeguards are addressed and respected' if they want to receive results-based payments. Many of the carbon crediting mechanisms base their requirements on the definitions and procedures created by the UNFCCC and initiatives (e.g., the World Bank Social and Environmental Safeguard Policies, the

Climate, Community and Biodiversity Standards, etc.). The most effective possibility to establish certain safeguards is by excluding activities that might have negative impacts.

2.2.9. *Summary: how environmental integrity of LMTs in general can be ensured?*

Including land-use activities into carbon market mechanisms aiming at offsetting under the PA raises environmental integrity challenges. In considering the role of the sector, key questions are for which type, and scale of activities environmental integrity risks are high, and, whether and how these risks can be appropriately addressed.

Table 1 provides an overview of the different environmental integrity risks and whether and how they can be addressed in the context of crediting mechanisms in general. Some environmental integrity risks uniquely apply to all land-use activities, while others differ substantially among different types of activities.

Moreover, many risks do not uniquely apply to land-use activities. This applies to issues of leakage and non-permanence, e.g., with the introduction of more efficient cook stoves.⁸ Regarding different crediting approaches, we find that some environmental integrity risks differ substantially among different types of activities, while others apply uniquely to all land-use activities (Table 1). Some risks seem also more material than others. In our assessment, risks related to additionality, baselines and leakage vary considerably among different types of activities.

⁸ See results for cook stoves at <https://carboncreditquality.org/>

Table 1: Environmental integrity risks for different types of land-use activities and whether and how they can be addressed with current approaches

	Afforestation and reforestation	Reduced deforestation or forest degradation	Improved forest management	Wetland management	Improved soil management	Biomass management	Agriculture
Determining baselines	Can be determined, as uncertainty of future developments is limited	Difficult to determine as it involves considerable uncertainty about future developments		Wetland restoration: Can be determined Wetland preservation: Difficult to determine due to uncertainties	Can be determined	Can be determined	Can be determined
Assessing additionality	Can be assessed	Difficult to assess	Difficult to assess	Wetland restoration: Can be assessed Wetland preservation: Difficult to assess	Can be assessed	Can be assessed	Can be assessed
Addressing non-permanence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot be ensured - risks can only be mitigated. Activities with high non-permanence risks should be excluded from crediting. Appropriate activity design, responsibility of project owners to monitor and compensate for reversals over long time horizons, coupled with sufficiently capitalised and diversified pooled buffer reserves, are best suited to reduce reversal risks. 				Regarding rice production (CH4 mitigation): non-permanence risk is limited; for the rest identical to what stands left.	Biochar: relatively permanent depending on climate zone & soil type, etc. BECCS: depends on type of storage Compost: risks can only be mitigated	Non-permanence due to management change relatively large
Addressing leakage	Depends on design of activity, e.g., status of land to be afforested	Depends on design of activity, e.g., deforestation drivers to be addressed	Depends on design of activity, e.g., forest products affected by activity	Depends on design of activity, e.g., alternative land uses considered	LMTs involving agricultural production have in general a high risk of leakage (due to market effects)	Minor risk	LMTs involving agricultural production have in general a high risk of leakage (due to market effects)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing the boundaries of land-use activities from projects to jurisdictional scale can avoid direct leakage within the jurisdiction. Activities causing global leakage should generally be excluded from crediting. 						
Visibility in GHG inventory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be achieved. Depends to lesser degree on activity than on granularity of GHG inventory. Inclusion of specific emissions factors and land area required; 						
Effective monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can effectively be done. Biomass pools can be monitored with higher accuracy than soil carbon pools. Global data and remote sensing can help to increase accuracy and consistency. Consistency between lower-level activities and national level reporting can be challenging. 						
Avoiding double counting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be avoided. Provisions to ensure unique claims to carbon stored in the land are important. 'Nested' accounting can avoid double issuance between jurisdictional approaches and crediting at project level. 						
Considering safeguards and co-benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can in general be considered. Risks and co-benefits are very context-specific: Land-use activities can pose risks but also considerable opportunities regarding adaptation, biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration. 						

Source: UBA 2022 and own contribution

2.3. Analysis of potential markets

2.3.1. Overview

Market-based approaches for reducing the release of GHG emissions or additional storage of carbon to mitigate climate change are systems that generate **carbon credits** as tradable certificates that represent a reduction in atmospheric CO₂ or an increase in carbon storage. Table 2 lists different terms for carbon credits that exist in current market mechanisms. There are two types of carbon credits that supply different markets: Voluntary Emission Reductions (VERs), sold in the **voluntary market**, and Certified Emission Reductions (CERs), sold in the **compliance market**.

Table 2: Carbon credit and trading units in carbon markets

Name	Abbreviation	Where used
Voluntary Emission Reductions	VER	Type of carbon credit generated in voluntary carbon markets
Certified Emission Reductions	CER	Type of carbon credit generated in compliance carbon markets
Temporary Certified Emission Reductions	tCER	Temporary certified emission reductions under CDM
Long-term Certified Emission Reductions	ICER	Long-term certified emission reductions under CDM
Assigned Amount Unit	AAU	Allowed emissions under the Kyoto Protocol
Removal Unit	RMU	Removals achieved through LULUCF activities under the Kyoto Protocol
Emission Reduction Unit	ERU	Unit generated from a Joint implementation project

Another way to differentiate approaches is by crediting mechanisms and emission trading schemes. **Crediting mechanisms** enable payments for achieved emission reductions or sink enhancements. It issues tradable certificates for actual emission reductions achieved and verified below a predetermined **baseline**. Crediting mechanisms require emission reductions or removals to be **additional**, i.e., that they occur because of the incentives created by carbon credit revenues. Crediting mechanisms often include activities at project level. If such activities affect GHG sources and carbon sinks in other sectors or outside the target area, **leakage** occurs and needs to be addressed to ensure environmental integrity of the crediting system. Participation in a crediting mechanism is voluntary. Supply of voluntary carbon credits comes mostly from private entities that develop carbon projects, or governments that develop programs certified by carbon standards that generate emission reductions or increased removals. Demand comes as well from private entities that strive to compensate for emissions, e.g., corporations with corporate sustainability targets, and other actors aiming to trade credits at a higher price to make a profit.

An **emissions trading scheme (cap-and-trade system)** sets a regulatory maximum emission level or ‘cap’ for sectors covered by the scheme. Only the quantity of emission permits (allowances) is issued that allow the reduction target to be met. Businesses under an emissions trading scheme need to get allowance for each tonne of CO₂ they emit. These allowances can be traded allowing participants to buy additional allowances or sell excess allowances they do not need. The scheme results in a carbon price that depends on the level of ambition applied when setting the maximum allowable emissions level and costs for implementing emission reduction measures.

Cap-and-trade mechanisms avoid some of the challenges of carbon crediting approaches (Böttcher et al. 2022b). They do not require assessing counterfactual scenarios regarding the additionality and baselines of specific mitigation activities. They also avoid leakage within the scope of the system because of their wide (often national) coverage. The main challenge of cap-and-trade mechanisms is establishing the **cap at a level that is sufficiently below the assumed business-as-usual**. Initial over-allocation of allowances in emissions trading schemes has been a major challenge in nearly all established emissions trading schemes.

Market-based approaches can also be differentiated by looking at the **type of payment**. **Activity-based payments** is financing paid ex ante for pre-defined activities, i.e., it is not results-based. Such kind of finance is provided for many REDD+ activities, e.g., finance for REDD+ readiness and implementation. Compared to activity-based payments **results-based finance** approaches provide payments ex post for the achievement of pre-defined and verified results, e.g., verified emission reductions or removals. Results-based finance can be differentiated further into **results-based payments** where the achieved emission reductions or removals are accounted for with their provider and in the host country without any transfer. Transfer-based payments instead allow for the achieved emission reductions or removals and their legal titles to be transferred to the buyer where they are counted against the buyer’s climate targets. Table 3 provides an overview of market opportunities. In the following we analyse these different carbon market options regarding their requirements, challenges, and opportunities for crediting land-based mitigation activities.

Table 3: Overview of market opportunities

	Voluntary mechanisms			Compliance mechanisms		
	Voluntary activity-based incentive schemes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms		Emissions trading schemes	Other cap-and-trade systems	Article 6 Paris Agreement
		For funding (results-based payments)	For offsetting (transfer-based payments)			
Examples	EU Eco-schemes	REDD+ Early Mover	CORSIA	EU ETS	Kyoto Protocol, EU LULUCF, EU ESR	
Reference	None	Baseline	Baseline	Cap	National target	Baseline
Use of credits	None	Funding	Offset/transfer	For achieving net reduction	For achieving national target	For achieving NDC target
Addressee	Private land-owners, farmers	Private land-owners, farmers	Private land-owners, farmers	Companies	States under regulation	Parties of the Paris Agreement
Scope of activities	Projects/Activities	Projects, jurisdictional, national	Projects, jurisdictional, national	Companies	National	National
Funding source for payments	Private sector, government	Private sector, government	Private sector	Private sector	Government	Governments
Governance of certification	Private and public schemes	Private schemes	Private schemes	Private and public schemes	UNFCCC rules, EU Regulation	Private schemes accredited by UN

2.3.2. Voluntary activity-based incentive schemes

The inclusion of LMTs in voluntary activity-based incentive schemes that are not results-based pose the lowest requirements. Such market mechanisms are not based on crediting of specific mitigation results, such as

emission reductions or sink enhancement. Instead, payments are granted for the implementation of activities or compensation for losses, e.g., due to changes in land management. An example for such payments is the EU Eco-schemes under the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Since no credits are generated, there is no need for establishing a baseline against which achievements are measured. The mere adoption of an activity qualifies for receiving payments. In voluntary markets such schemes typically address private landowners and farmers that implement projects or adopt activities. These are funded by the private sector or government institutions. There are private and public schemes of governance of certification, depending on the set up of the market mechanism.

While baselines, non-permanence and double counting issues are less relevant for such types of market mechanisms, additionality remains an important requirement, e.g., requiring that activities go beyond the legal obligation of those who receive payments.

Adopted activities might change production levels and thus cause leakage, e.g., the shift of activities to other areas causing damage to the environment and thus undermining the primary aim of the market instrument. However, reducing leakage is usually not a requirement of the mechanisms themselves but needs to be addressed by other policies. The requirements for monitoring are typically limited to a documentation of the implementation or abandonment of an activity.

LMTs in voluntary activity-based incentive schemes that are not results-based do not require necessarily visibility in GHG inventories, however, since they are expected to contribute to achieving national GHG mitigation targets visibility increases their effectiveness as an instrument for achieving national or regional GHG mitigation targets. Important are also safeguards to prevent trade-offs with other targets and measures to realise co-benefits when implementing activities. Table 4 summarises the assumptions on requirements for voluntary incentive schemes regarding ‘environmental integrity’.

Table 4: Assumptions on requirements for voluntary incentive schemes regarding ‘environmental integrity’

Market	Voluntary incentive schemes	Justification
Baselines	(No)	Baselines can play a role for giving access to voluntary incentive schemes. However, they are not used for crediting or assessing results.
Additionality	Yes	Voluntary incentive schemes typically do not reward legal compliance, thus require that recipients go beyond a certain status or standard behaviour.
Non-permanence	No	Voluntary incentive schemes are oriented towards activities and do not account for reversals of mitigation results that might occur.
Leakage risks	(No)	Voluntary incentive schemes can cause leakage reducing their effectiveness but is addressed through additional policies and measures.
Monitoring	(No)	Requirements for monitoring limited to a documentation of the implementation or abandonment of an activity.
Visibility in GHG inventory	(No)	Visibility increases the effectiveness of voluntary incentive schemes as policy instrument.
Double counting	Yes	Double counting issues for voluntary incentive schemes occur in the form of double claiming. Payment schemes usually cannot be cumulated.
Safeguards and co-benefits	Yes	Required to reduce trade-offs with other targets and realise co-benefits when implementing activities.

2.3.3. Voluntary crediting mechanisms

For funding (results-based payments)

Voluntary results-based crediting mechanisms require crediting of specific mitigation results, such as an emission reduction or sink enhancement. Results achieved are not being traded but rather used for domestic purposes, e.g., by a government for achieving national targets. An example for such payments are results-based payments under the REDD+ Early Mover Programme⁹ but also activities adopted under the EU Carbon Farming Initiative (EC 2021a), such as peatland rewetting, agroforestry, SOC enhancement.

The credits generated under such schemes require the establishment of a baseline against which achievements are measured. In this sense results-based payments differ from activity-based incentive schemes. Requirements for additionality are lower compared to mechanisms where credits are traded. Nevertheless, investors in such markets demand evidence that activities were triggered by their payments.

Under voluntary crediting mechanisms without the trade of mitigation results, private landowners and farmers are funded by the private sector or government institutions with typically private schemes of governance of certification. An example was the species-rich grassland scheme (MEKA B4) in Baden-Württemberg, Germany (2007-2013). It was using as result indicator the presence of at least four indicator species for extensive grassland (out of a total list of 28 species). Farmers were free to determine how to manage the species-rich grassland with respect to cutting time, stocking density and fertiliser use (Russi et al. 2016). Another example of bilateral results-based payments is the Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF) through that Indonesia receives payments for its efforts to lower carbon emissions from deforestation and forest degradation.

Assumptions on the baseline and the consideration of non-permanence issues are relevant for such type of market mechanisms because payments might depend on the level of performance. Double counting risks are limited due to the non-tradability of credits.

Activities under voluntary crediting mechanisms for funding might change production levels and thus cause leakage. However, reducing leakage is usually not a requirement of the mechanisms themselves but needs to be addressed by other policies. Monitoring forms the basis for crediting of the achieved emission reductions or increased removals, therefore requirements are higher compared to voluntary incentive schemes.

LMTs in voluntary results-based crediting mechanisms require visibility in GHG inventories to demonstrate their effectiveness for achieving national or regional GHG mitigation targets. Important are also safeguards to limit trade-offs with other targets and measures to realise co-benefits when implementing activities.

Table 5 summarises the assumptions on requirements for voluntary crediting mechanisms for funding regarding 'environmental integrity'.

⁹ <https://www.kfw-entwicklungsbank.de/International-financing/KfW-Development-Bank/Topics/Climate/REDD/>

Table 5: Assumptions on requirements for voluntary crediting mechanisms for funding regarding ‘environmental integrity’

Market	Voluntary crediting mechanisms For funding (results-based finance)	Justification
Baselines	Yes	Payments under voluntary crediting mechanisms might depend on the level of performance.
Additionality	Yes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms require additionality to be cost-effective from the investors point of view.
Non-permanence	Yes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms account for reversals of mitigation results that might occur.
Leakage risks	(No)	Adopted activities might change production levels but voluntary crediting schemes usually do take it into account.
Monitoring	Yes	Monitoring forms the basis for crediting of the achieved emission reductions or increased removals.
Visibility in GHG inventory	(Yes)	Visibility in GHG inventories is important for the host of an activity to document achievement of target with the help of the mechanism.
Double counting	No	Risks are limited due to the non-tradability of credits.
Safeguards and co-benefits	Yes	Required to reduce trade-offs with other targets and realise co-benefits when implementing activities.

For offsetting (transfer-based payments)

Results-based crediting mechanisms aiming at transferring results for the purpose of offsetting have the highest requirements for environmental integrity among voluntary schemes. Example for frameworks that adopt such systems are CORSIA and the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework proposed in 2022 (EC 2022) but also the voluntary private market of GHG offsetting and compensation. Examples for standards in such crediting mechanisms are ART TREES, VCS, Gold Standard, etc.

The credits generated under such schemes require the establishment of a baseline against which achievements are measured. Also, requirements for additionality are high because emission reduction or removal results are traded. In these markets private landowners and farmers are funded by the private sector or government institutions with typically private schemes of governance of certification.

Payments under voluntary crediting mechanisms for transfer require credible baseline estimates. Therefore, assumptions on the baseline and also non-permanence issues are relevant for such type of market mechanisms. Also including the risk of double counting. Change of production levels and leakage is a serious threat for credibility of voluntary crediting mechanisms for offsetting. Existing schemes take it into account. There are usually explicit rules for how to reduce the risk of leakage under crediting mechanisms, e.g., by appropriate project design. If leakage cannot be avoided, it needs to be quantified and included in the crediting. Monitoring requirements are high as it forms the basis for crediting achieved emission reductions or increased removals. There are detailed procedures and methods elaborated by standards, often also building on IPCC methodologies.

LMTs in voluntary results-based crediting mechanisms require visibility in GHG inventories to demonstrate their effectiveness for achieving national or regional GHG mitigation targets. Important are also safeguards that are typically required by standards to avoid trade-offs with other targets and realise co-benefits when implementing activities.

Table 6: Assumptions on requirements for voluntary crediting mechanisms for offsetting regarding 'environmental integrity'

Market	Voluntary crediting mechanisms For offsetting (transfer-based finance)	Justification
Baselines	Yes	Payments under voluntary crediting mechanisms for transfer require credible baseline estimates
Additionality	Yes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms require additionality to be cost-effective and achieve additional net GHG mitigation.
Non-permanence	Yes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms for offsetting take into account mitigation results and thus need to account for reversals.
Leakage risks	Yes	Change of production levels and subsequent leakage is a serious threat for credibility of voluntary crediting mechanisms for offsetting. Existing schemes take it into account.
Monitoring	Yes	Monitoring forms the basis for crediting of the achieved emission reductions or increased removals.
Visibility in GHG inventory	(Yes)	Visibility in GHG inventories is important to document that the mechanism contributes to achieving a target.
Double counting	Yes	Risks of double claiming, double issuance and double use need to be addressed.
Safeguards and co-benefits	Yes	Required to reduce trade-offs with other targets and realise co-benefits when implementing activities.

2.3.4. Emissions trading schemes

Emissions trading schemes (ETS) constitute a type of cap-and-trade system in which a maximum amount of emissions for the regulated entities in the system are allowed. The allowances issued or sold to entities can be traded with other participants in the ETS. Examples for ETS are the ETS of the European Union and the New Zealand (NZ) ETS (Leining 2016).

The NZ ETS is the only scheme in the world that includes the forestry sector. As of 2019, besides forestry, also waste, industry and energy sectors have obligations to report GHG emissions and surrender units, covering around 54% of New Zealand's emissions. The ETS rules applying to the forestry sector were designed to align with the requirements of the Kyoto Protocol and to help New Zealand meet its related obligations. In its first NDC, NZ has broadly outlined the accounting methodologies it will apply for the LULUCF sector to assess achievement of its 2030 target under the Paris Agreement.

The EU ETS is operational since 2005 and covers about 45 % of EU GHG emissions¹⁰. The system currently covers the energy sector and energy-intensive parts of the industry sector, as well as aviation within the EU. The system has been revised several times throughout the years, for example through the inclusion of a market stability reserve and changes with respect to the allocation of emission allowances. In 2021, the European Commission

¹⁰ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en

proposed to establish a new EU ETS to cover the sectors road transport and buildings (EC 2021b). Addressees in existing ETS are companies and other operators of large energy and industry installations. Funding is generated through the trade among participants governed by a common price for CO₂.

The requirements for environmental integrity differ from those for voluntary crediting mechanisms as they usually do not include specific rules for addressing non-permanence risks. This is due to the nature of the cap-and-trade system in which reversals of emission reductions or removals are covered and thus priced-in by the system. In the case of the EU ETS, however, additional regulation is provided through the EU’s [Carbon Capture and Storage Directive](#)¹¹. To ensure safe geological storage of CO₂. CCS projects need to conduct an [Environmental Impact Assessment \(EIA\)](#) addressing possible non-permanence risks. Baselines for individual activities potentially covered by an ETS are derived from the current level of emissions from these activities. Based on the emission reduction target to be achieved with the ETS these are then translated into a sector specific cap of maximum emission levels accepted in the system.

Table 7. Assumptions on requirements for Emission Trading Schemes regarding ‘environmental integrity’

Market	Emission Trading Schemes	Justification
Baselines	(Yes)	ETS use current emission levels as baseline to allocate individual allowances under a common cap of maximum emissions.
Additionality	No	ETS do not require additionality as they consider a closed system in which emissions need to be reduced.
Non-permanence	No	In cap-and-trade systems reversals of emission reductions or removals are covered and thus priced-in by the system.
Leakage risks	(No)	Leakage risks in general exist but are not addressed by the ETS.
Monitoring	Yes	Effective monitoring is needed for a fair allocation of allowances but also for a robust governance.
Visibility in GHG inventory	Yes	Visibility in GHG inventories is important to document that the mechanism contributes to achieving a target.
Double counting	Yes	Risks of double counting exist, especially if the coupling of different systems occurs. They are addressed by the European Union Registry for the ETS.
Safeguards and co-benefits	(Yes)	Required to reduce trade-offs with other targets, e.g., sustainability of biomass use in ETS.

The level of the cap has proven to be a decisive element for the effectiveness of ETS for achieving actual emission reductions. Less relevant are issues of additionality within ETS, as they consider a closed system in which emissions need to be reduced. Instead, leakage risks can be high if production can be easily relocated to places outside the ETS. However, reducing leakage is usually not required by ETS participants themselves but needs to be addressed by other policies. The EU has taken measures to identify sectors with high leakage risks and measures to address the risk¹². Free allowances are directed towards the sectors with highest leakage exposure,

¹¹ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/carbon-capture-use-and-storage_en

¹² https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/free-allocation/carbon-leakage_en

in which allowances are distributed individual installation based on their efficiency. Such risks can be addressed by introducing CO₂ taxes for imports (e.g., EU Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism¹³).

Emission trading schemes require effective monitoring systems that allow for a fair allocation of allowances but also for a robust governance of the ETS. Double counting issues can be relevant in case of transfers between ETS and the coupling of different systems, e.g., voluntary crediting mechanisms and ETS that are, however, currently not allowed. Some ETS include requirements for safeguards and co-benefits on how the emission reductions are achieved. For example, the EU ETS has in place safeguards for ensuring the sustainability of biomass used under the EU ETS¹⁴.

2.3.5. *Other cap-and-trade systems*

Besides the EU ETS the EU climate policy includes other systems that can be counted under cap-and-trade in the wider sense. Emissions under the recently revised Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) are regulated through binding annual GHG emission targets for each EU Member State based on the principles of fairness, cost-effectiveness and environmental integrity¹⁵. These commitments specify emission reduction targets for the agriculture, buildings and transport sectors as well as other emissions not covered by the EU ETS. The Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation has also recently been revised and regulates emissions and removals from forests, cropland, grassland, settlements, wetlands and harvested wood products. It requires Member States to achieve a net zero target for the LULUCF sector in the period 2021-2025 applying specific accounting rules and a total EU net removal target of -310 Mt CO₂ in 2030 that is allocated to national binding removal targets at Member State level (European Commission 2021).

There are flexibilities within and between ESR and LULUCF Regulation that are supposed to support compliance of Member States in a cost-efficient manner. Under the LULUCF Regulation units can be traded over time, between countries, and between ESR and LULUCF Regulation with country specific limitations. EU Member States can thus act as sellers (in the case of excess of credits) and buyers (in the case of debits) in GHG accounting towards their targets.

In the mentioned EU policies baselines play a central role by providing a basis for target setting. EU ESR targets have been set using per capita GDP information. Under the LULUCF an EU-wide target of -310 Mt CO₂ was set based on the projection of emissions and removals assuming increased efforts of Member States compared to a reference scenario (Böttcher et al. 2022a).

A crucial element for ensuring environmental integrity of including the land-use sector in cap-and-trade systems are well designed accounting rules. Current rules applied under the EU LULUCF Regulation for the first period 2021-2025 differentiate between different activities (e.g., afforestation gross-net accounting, managed cropland net-net accounting, managed forest accounting against a projected reference level). Accounting rules involving projections have proven to be not transparent and therefore difficult to review and reconcile.

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_21_3661

¹⁴ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/gd3_biomass_issues_en.pdf

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_21_3543

Accounting land use under cap-and-trade mechanisms using a so called ‘net-net approach’ can significantly increase transparency if periods for establishing the reference are close to the accounting period.

The LULUCF Regulation requires reporting and accounting at the level of land use categories (land-based approach compared to activity-based approach). All emissions and removals occurring on managed land need to be included. As of 2026 the LULUCF Regulation covers all land use categories that count towards the national net removal target and abandons accounting against reference values. This comprehensive accounting approach makes a consideration of additionality obsolete as only total emission reductions or removal increases are counted. However, an appropriate integration of such systems into the wider climate policy, e.g., through separate emission reduction and removal targets as set by the EU, is critical to avoid that removals occurring anyway are rewarded and used to offset emissions in other sectors.

The rules for reporting set by IPCC reduce the risk of double counting as it might, e.g., occur between trading countries. As emissions and removals need to be included continuously over time, there is also no issue with potential non-permanence. The LULUCF Regulation includes provisions on how Member States can exclude emissions caused by extreme events to be considered beyond control of the country. However, the exclusion requires a geographically explicit documentation and an exclusion of subsequent removals on the affected areas. Leakage risks do exist, especially due to very different ambition levels between EU and other world regions. However, it is not required by the regulated countries but needs to be addressed by other policies, e.g., the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products¹⁶. In general, monitoring requirements are high for these systems as they rely on accurate and complete GHG reporting. Nevertheless, completeness and accuracy are still major challenges for Member States, especially regarding soil emissions for which regular inventories are costly and support from remote sensing technologies limited.

Table 8: Assumptions on requirements for other cap-and-trade systems regarding ‘environmental integrity’

Market	Other cap-and-trade systems (EU LULUCF, EU ESR)	Justification
Baselines	Yes	Baselines in cap-and-trade systems play a central role by providing a basis for target setting. Baselines can be part of specific accounting rules.
Additionality	No	Like ETS, other cap-and-trade systems do not require additionality as they consider a closed system in which targets need to be achieved.
Non-permanence	No	In cap-and-trade systems reversals of emission reductions or removals are covered. Special rules might apply for dealing with natural disturbances.
Leakage risks	No	Leakage risks in general exist if production shifts to outside the system occur but they are not addressed by cap-and-trade systems themselves.
Monitoring	Yes	Monitoring and reporting in GHG inventories forms the basis of cap-and-trade systems. It is essential for target setting and governance.
Visibility in GHG inventory	Yes	Visibility in GHG inventories is essential for an effective cap-and-trade system.
Double counting	No	Risks of double counting exist, especially if there are flexibilities and trade allowed with other systems and between participants.
Safeguards and co-benefits	Yes	Required to reduce trade-offs with other targets.

¹⁶ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-regulation-deforestation-free-products_en

2.3.6. *Article 6 Paris Agreement*

All Parties to the Paris Agreement have committed to contribute to achieving its goal and to regularly pledge mitigation contributions in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Article 6 of the Paris Climate Agreement establishes that Parties may elect to cooperate with other countries to achieve mitigation goals by trading emissions credits or offsets. The NDCs typically specify whether they intend to use such mechanisms to achieve their contributions. Analysis of newly submitted NDCs finds that 83%, versus 67% previously, say they might include such mechanisms¹⁷.

Article 6.2 of the Paris Agreement establishes a framework for Parties to engage in ‘cooperative approaches’ that involve the use of ‘internationally transferred mitigation outcomes’ (ITMOs) towards NDCs, and Article 6.4 establishes a new crediting mechanism to contribute to the mitigation of GHG emissions and support sustainable development (Article 6.4 mechanism). In addition, many carbon market approaches are being implemented by governments and non-state-actors. These can be used for various purposes, including for international cooperation under Article 6, as national climate policies to achieve NDCs, or as voluntary action to reduce emissions. This report considers various carbon market approaches but with a focus on their potential use under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (Table 9).

To determine the contribution of the land-use sector to the achievement of NDCs, emissions and removals must be quantified and accounted using comparable and consistent approaches. The reporting of emissions and removals from the land-use sector is based on internationally agreed rules for national GHG inventories and aims at documenting the level and development of GHG emissions and removals over time. The main basis is the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories (IPCC 2006). These have recently been amended by the so-called ‘2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories’ adopted in 2019 (IPCC 2019). However, so far, only the 2006 IPCC Guidelines must be used within the framework of the Paris Agreement.

Under the PA, Article 13 establishes an ‘enhanced transparency framework’ to report GHG emissions and removals and to track progress towards the implementation and achievement of NDCs. This framework has been operationalised through the adoption of the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’ (MPGs) at COP24 in Katowice (decision 18/CMA.1). The MPGs provide an overarching accounting concept, including the land-use sector. Important elements for accounting for the land-use sector are also included in decision 4/CMA.1, which lists information that countries should include in their NDCs to provide clarity and provides guidelines for how countries should account for their NDCs.

Principals and requirements for the usability of LMTs are:

- Enhancing ambition,
- Overall mitigation in global emissions (OMGE),
- Additionality and attribution of emission reductions,
- Robust quantification of emission reductions and removals,
- Robust Accounting,

¹⁷ <https://www.wri.org/insights/understanding-ndcs-paris-agreement-climate-pledges>

- Addressing non-permanence risks,
- Transparency, including in governance,
- Enhancing positive and preventing negative environmental and social impacts.

Potential market participants under the PA are countries seeking for emission reductions and removals from LMTs to achieve their NDCs certified by private schemes accredited by the UNFCCC.

Table 9: Assumptions on requirements for Article 6 under the Paris Agreement regarding ‘environmental integrity’

Market	Article 6 Paris Agreement	Justification
Baselines	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Additionality	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Non-permanence	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Leakage risks	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Monitoring	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Visibility in GHG inventory	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Double counting	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’
Safeguards and co-benefits	Yes	Addressed in the ‘Modalities, procedures and guidelines for the transparency framework for action and support’

2.3.7. Summary of requirements

Table 10 provides a summary of market opportunities and requirements towards different aspects of environmental integrity. It forms the basis for evaluating environmental integrity and resulting market opportunities for different LMTs in the case studies covered. The details of the analysis of potential markets and their requirements are provided in the following.

Table 10: Summary of requirements of potential markets towards aspects of environmental integrity

	Voluntary mechanisms			Compliance mechanisms		
	Voluntary activity-based incentive schemes	Voluntary crediting mechanisms		Emissions trading schemes	Other cap-and-trade systems	Article 6 Paris Agreement
		For funding (results-based payments)	For offsetting (transfer-based payments)			
Baselines	(NO)	YES	YES	(YES)	YES	YES
Additionality	Yes	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES
Non-permanence	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES
Leakage risks	(NO)	(NO)	YES	(YES)	NO	YES
Monitoring	(NO)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Visibility in GHG inventory	(NO)	(YES)	(YES)	YES	YES	YES
Double counting	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES
Safeguards and co-benefits	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

2.4. Assessing environmental integrity risks of LMT activities

Based on the analysis above we developed a survey that summarises essential aspects related to risks for environmental integrity of LMT implementation and resulting market opportunities. The survey aims at providing a basis for information and capacity building among decision makers concerned with the implementation of LMTs. This will ensure that the LMT solutions presented in the case studies of the LANDMARC project can potentially be integrated into existing international and national climate policies and will contribute to unlocking the potential of carbon offset market for LMT finance.

The survey was developed as a checklist and converted into an online survey¹⁸. The initial criteria to select the use cases where the coverage of the LMTs, the geographical coverage, different markets of carbon crediting, different MRV approaches and the capacity of the project partner.

In total, 12 case studies contributed information on their LMTs. It is important to note that within this survey the LANDMARC case study leaders were asked to make a self-assessment on the different aspects of environmental integrity for the specific LMT activity in their country. There is no link to any public or private certification scheme.

The Table 11 displays which LMTs, mitigation types and case studies have been included in the survey. The list can potentially be extended to all case studies in the LANDMARC project.

¹⁸ <https://forms.office.com/e/N1aFaHTxLZ>

Table 11: Coverage of LMT types in survey

LMTs	Climate effect	Case study examples
Afforestation and reforestation	Increasing C removals	Agroforestry (Netherlands)
		Agroforestry (Burkina Faso)
Improved forest management	Increasing C removals	Forest Management (Germany)
Improved soil management	Preserving C stocks, Reducing emission	Integrated soil fertility management (Kenya)
		Biogas: methane capture from animal manure, reduce N ₂ O emissions from synthetic fertilizers (Indonesia)
		Improved rice management, dry seeded rice (Nepal)
	Preserving C stocks, Increasing C removals	Organic agriculture (Switzerland) Reduced / No-tillage (Switzerland)
Wetland management	Preserving C stocks, Increasing C removals Reducing emissions	Restore damage ecosystems back into their biological function in the context of boreal forests (Canada)
		Wetland management (Netherlands)
Biomass management	Preserving C stocks	Biochar (Sweden)
	Reducing emission	BECCS (Sweden)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. What is the empirical evidence regarding environmental integrity from case studies?

We analysed responses of 12 case studies to the survey. In the following, we discuss selected preliminary results of the survey. Annex 2 of the report includes a summary of answers to all questions.

Figure 1 shows the representation of geographical scope. The LANDMARC case studies cover a wide variety of scopes that is resulting in different opportunities for carbon market engagement. While farm and field level projects are more suitable for voluntary crediting mechanisms, the national level is more likely to be addressed through cap-and-trade mechanisms.

What is the geographical scope?

Figure 1: Representation of geographical scope of LMTs in case studies covered by the survey

Baselines are an essential element of most carbon market mechanisms and required for all options, except voluntary incentive schemes. With regard to the survey, six out of 12 cases, responded with “yes” whether baselines have been established or not (Figure 2). There is a larger amount of “no answer” to the question of baselines which shows that there are also cases where there is still a lack of information on the matter. The requirements for baselines will be a central element for planned training material that can be used by project partners (concept for a seminar, including suggested speakers, material for presentation) and topic in internal seminars.

Has a baseline been established?

Figure 2: Existence of a baseline

In Figure 3 answers of case studies are presented regarding the question whether an additionality assessment exists. Additionality is a crucial requirement, especially for voluntary crediting mechanisms but also simple incentive schemes. It is less relevant for compliance systems. For five out of 12 case studies, additionality has been assessed but also six of 12 indicate a lack of information (no answer, don't know).

Has additionality been assessed?

Figure 3: Existence of an additionality assessment

Regarding non-permanence, for 9 of 12 case studies, the risk was assessed to be medium or high. However, only in five cases studies permanence is monitored (Figure 4) by field measurements, field measurements combined with information from earth observation, and comparison to a reference projects. This implies considerable risks for environmental integrity and thus constraints for market opportunities, especially in the field of voluntary crediting mechanisms. There are considerable differences between existing standards regarding the minimum monitoring period during which carbon stocks needs to be controlled. Land-based mitigation options bear an inherent risk that emissions reduced, or carbon stored is released, thus emission reductions or removals are reversed.

Non-permanence risks vary with carbon pools and LMT types but also with project design. Non-permanence has also implications for the potential use of credits. Credits that cannot guarantee permanent storage of carbon (this can basically only be guaranteed by geological storage) should not be used for offsetting fossil fuel emissions. Therefore, crediting mechanisms should constrain the use of credits to non-offsetting uses. This makes them less attractive for markets and thus reduces potential funding for LMT implementation. However,

it needs to be secured that overall GHG mitigation occurs, otherwise the effectiveness of these instruments can be doubted.

Figure 4: The likelihood of non-permanence and existence of monitoring

For 9 out of 12 case studies leakage risks are known. There is also considerable knowledge about how leakage can be reduced. The survey did not explore further details on LMT project design. Options for risk reduction mentioned by survey participants are:

- Use of residual biomass / Controlled use of biochar on crops,
- regulated use of bioenergy (energy penalty effect and surplus energy needed to capture carbon)
- sourcing of organic materials from within the farm,
- capacity building through training,
- and restoring land that is degraded.

These are well in line with approaches also considered by existing crediting mechanisms. Leakage risks are a general concern of land-based mitigation options. Careful project design, like the implementation of afforestation on abandoned land can reduce risks of leakage. Leakage effects that cannot be avoided need to be quantified and included in the crediting.

Figure 5: Risk of leakage (left panel) and the role of project design (right panel)

There is a lack of information regarding the visibility of LMT implementation in national GHG inventories among case studies for 6 out of 12 responses (Figure 5). Visibility in GHG inventories is an important requirement for compliance systems. For crediting mechanisms, it is also needed for ensuring that the activities funded through the mechanisms are reducing emissions or enhance sinks at the national level and thus support compliance of the country with national targets.

Is the considered implementation of LMT represented in GHG inventory?

Figure 5: Visibility in GHG inventory

More information in case studies exist about potential negative impacts of LMT implementation (Figure 6). Safeguards and co-benefits are a requirement for almost all market opportunities, except ETS.

Do potential negative direct impacts and risks exist?

Figure 6: Information about potential negative impacts of LMT implementation in case studies

3.2. Implications for market opportunities

This survey identifies key issues of LMT implementation in case studies regarding environmental integrity and market opportunities. The results show for each case study that key questions related to environmental integrity could not always be answered fully (Table 12). This can be either lack of information, lack of knowledge about key methodological aspects of environmental integrity, or a negative result of an evaluation.

The list of aspects presented in an overview matrix compares available information with requirements for different market opportunities (Table 13). While requirements for monitoring but also safeguards and co-benefits seem to be addressed by almost all case studies, additionality, non-permanence, and leakage risks are

aspects addressed by less than 50% of the case study leaders. This potentially has implications for opportunities for carbon markets (Table 13).

Through issues of lack of information regarding specific LMTs in the LANDMARC case studies can be identified. However, it is important to note that these results can hardly be used for an assessment of specific project situations. A general conclusion on whether certain projects in carbon markets constitute a risk for environmental integrity is not possible. Key guiding questions for a differentiated assessment of the risk need to consider the type of activity and its scale and how potential risks can be appropriately addressed. In assessing these risks, the report has looked at available methods that are already common practice in the voluntary carbon market and existing cap-and-trade systems.

An important constraint is that within this survey LANDMARC case study leaders were asked to make a self-assessment on the different aspects of environmental integrity for the specific LMT activity in their country. No specific schemes were assessed, that could only be done looking at the specific situation of a project and the detailed methodologies to be applied under a crediting mechanism.

Table 12: Comparison of case study information with requirements for environmental integrity

Case study description	Baselines	Additionality	Non-permanence	Leakage risks	Monitoring	Visibility in GHG inventory	Double counting	Safeguards and co-benefits
Germany - Improved forest management - Extension of rotation length, forest protection, forestry adaptation (change of species composition)	OK	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Sweden - Biomass management - Biochar	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Sweden - Biomass management - BECCS	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Netherlands - Afforestation and Reforestation - Agroforestry	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK
Netherlands - Wetland management - Paludiculture	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK
Kenya (other SSA countries also make sense) - Improved soil management - Integrated soil fertility management (combine organic inputs, mineral fertilizer and improved varieties of maize)	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Switzerland - Improved soil management - Organic agriculture	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Switzerland - Improved soil management - Reduced/ No-tillage	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Indonesia - Improved soil management - Biogas: reduce fossil fuel (LPG) and firewood usage, methane capture from animal manure, reduce N2O from synthetic fertilizers	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK
Canada - Wetland restoration and protection - Restore damage ecosystems back into their biological function in the context of boreal forests	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK
Nepal - Improved rice management - Dry seeded rice	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK
Burkina Faso - Afforestation and Reforestation - Agroforestry	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED

* Art. 6.2 & Art. 6.4. refers only to the carbon market under the Paris Agreement

OK	According, to the provided answers, the LMT fulfills the requirements of the respective criteria
TO BE ADDRESSED	According, the provided answers, the LMT lacks requirements of the respective criteria

Table 13: Comparison of case study information with requirements for ‘environmental integrity’ for different market opportunities

Case study description	Voluntary incentive schemes	Voluntary carbon markets for funding (results-based)	Voluntary carbon markets for offsetting (transfer-based)	ETS	Cap-and-trade	Article 6
Germany - Improved forest management - Extension of rotation length, forest protection, forestry adaptation (change of species composition)	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED
Sweden - Biomass management - Biochar	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED
Sweden - Biomass management - BECCS	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED
Netherlands - Afforestation and Reforestation - Agroforestry	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Netherlands - Wetland management - Paludiculture	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Kenya (other SSA countries also make sense) - Improved soil management - Integrated soil fertility management (combine organic inputs, mineral fertilizer and improved varieties of maize)	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Switzerland - Improved soil management - Organic agriculture	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Switzerland - Improved soil management - Reduced/ No-tillage	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Indonesia - Improved soil management - Biogas: reduce fossil fuel (LPG) and firewood usage, methane capture from animal manure, reduce N2O from synthetic fertilizers	OK	OK	OK	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Canada - Wetland restoration and protection - Restore damage ecosystems back into their biological function in the context of boreal forests	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Nepal - Improved rice management - Dry seeded rice	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED
Burkina Faso - Afforestation and Reforestation - Agroforestry	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED	TO BE ADDRESSED

3.3. Addressing environmental integrity through constraining the use of mitigation

The challenges of crediting land-based mitigation activities result to some degree from the **intended use of mitigation results** generated. Issues with double counting, especially double use and double issuance occur mostly when the use of credits is targeted towards offsetting, i.e., compensation of fossil fuel emissions. This is independent from the type of LMT and the way the project is set up.

Demand for credits for offsetting purposes has been a major driver for the expansion of voluntary crediting mechanisms and a huge number of different standards in recent years. However, **continuing and enhancing trade with offsetting credits under the PA might cause several challenges:**

- Claiming carbon neutrality through offsetting may divert attention from the fact that, to meet the objectives of the Paris Agreement, emissions need be brought down to zero worldwide.
- Sellers of such credits might be incentivised to limit the extent to which they set own ambition in reducing emissions.
- There is a risk for buyers of offset credits related to additionality of the emissions reduction projects as under the Paris Agreement all countries have own emission reduction targets requiring a redefinition of additionality.

Among others, NewClimate institute proposes the concept of **'climate responsibility'**¹⁹ as an alternative to offsetting emissions and the aim of carbon neutrality based on offsets. The concept constitutes a transparent mechanism that reduces participants direct climate impact and at the same time channels financial resources to initiatives that are supposed to deliver real impact in addressing climate. The concept foresees six elements:

1. Tracking emissions with the aim to improve the understanding of emissions impact and remaining reduction potentials.
2. Reducing emissions as much as possible with a vision of real zero emissions.
3. Pricing emissions based on costs of emission and climate change impacts or costs for achieving PA goals and generating funds.
4. Using funds to support action for transformational change to address climate change.
5. Mainstreaming pricing and integrating costs into internal decision making.
6. Communicating transparently on lessons learnt to encourage replication.

However, buyers of offsetting credits who have built brand recognition on the claim of carbon neutrality may find the concept unattractive. This might change with an increasing consumer awareness on responsible climate action. To increase climate mitigation ambition also in developing countries, more financial support is needed, involving that from voluntary carbon markets. An important argument for the approach is that the determined price per tonne is not based on minimising costs of the project but based on a price signal aligned with the objectives of the Paris Agreement. Thus, the volume of climate finance flows could exceed the flow under the continuation of classical market approaches.

For sellers of mitigation results under carbon crediting mechanisms, i.e., implementers of LMT solutions and project developers, the concept of climate responsibility could entail an important shift away from a system that strives for least cost solutions. In fact, shortcomings of the current voluntary carbon market are a) a lack of common minimum standard criteria to ensure a level playing field for carbon credits also across different LMT types and b) the need to offer carbon credits at competitive prices, and c) a lack of transparency regarding the level of quality. Carbon prices in the voluntary market can easily range from a few Euros per ton of CO₂ to several hundred Euros per ton of CO₂. Under such conditions the price does not provide a good proxy of quality of

¹⁹ <https://newclimate.org/climateresponsibility>

carbon credits. This leaves buyers with a risk of purchasing low quality credits that do not only harm the environment but also the buyer's reputation.

A system in which the carbon price does not set by costs of the project offers opportunities for generating high quality carbon credits reflecting rather costs of the avoided damage CO₂ causes in the atmosphere. It allows also to include more easily co-benefits and non-carbon results in project implementation.

The concept of climate responsibility does not imply lowering standards for monitoring and carbon crediting. It still requires that implementers of LMT solutions adequately quantify mitigation results against credible baselines. However, it might free project implementers from the need to provide high accuracy estimates but rather encourage them to apply the principle of conservativeness. This means that method for crediting results guarantees that results are rather underestimated. This is important to reduce incentives for project implementers to inflate baselines, underestimate leakage risks and conceal risks of non-permanence.

The issue of transparency of methods for assessing mitigation results under crediting mechanisms needs to be addressed independently of the use of carbon credits.

Founded by Environmental Defense Fund, World Wildlife Fund (WWF-US) and Oeko-Institut, the Carbon Credit Quality Initiative (CCQI) provides transparent information on the quality of carbon credits²⁰. The analysis enables users to understand what types of carbon credits are more likely to deliver actual emission reductions as well as social and environmental benefits. The assessment draws on available research on carbon credit quality and a review by stakeholders. CCQI provides a detailed assessment of carbon credit quality against multiple criteria to enable buyers make more informed decisions. LMT practitioners and other stakeholders can use results of the initiative to draw conclusion for their specific project design to ensure high quality of the mitigation results to be achieved.

²⁰ <https://carboncreditquality.org/>

4. Conclusions

With this report we provide guidance and support to case study leads as the main target group and other readers such as LANDMARC stakeholders, policy makers, in three ways:

1. Introduction and thematic background on challenges of integrating LMTs into climate policy instruments, with a special focus on carbon market mechanisms;
2. Elaboration of specific risks for environmental integrity of LMTs including description of risk, challenges and approaches for risk mitigation (literature review and review of existing market mechanisms);
3. Presentation of a protocol for assessing environmental integrity and marketability in the format of a survey addressing case study leads and an analysis of results of the survey among 12 LANDMARC case studies.

We identified **environmental integrity** as a comprehensive concept that is widely used for assessing market mechanisms for climate change mitigation. Environmental integrity is referred to as the aim to:

- ensure permanence of emission reductions or carbon removals,
- demonstrate of additionality of mitigation activities,
- establish credible baselines,
- address the risk of leakage from shifting of activities,
- quantify net carbon storage with effective monitoring systems,
- avoid double counting, and
- establish safeguards to reduce negative impacts and generate co-benefits.

We identified **general requirements for mandatory and voluntary market mechanisms** for different types of LMTs and translated the requirements into different marketing opportunities. Through a survey we assessed issues of lack of information regarding specific LMTs in the LANDMARC case studies. It is important to note that these results can hardly be used for an assessment of specific **project** situations. A general conclusion on whether certain projects in carbon markets constitute a risk for environmental integrity is not possible. Key guiding questions for a differentiated assessment of the risk need to consider the type of activity and its scale and how potential risks can be appropriately addressed. In assessing these risks, the deliverable has looked at available methods that are already common practice in the voluntary carbon market and existing cap-and-trade systems.

Approaches developed by different mechanisms exist to:

- **Avoid** risks by selection of mitigation and project type (e.g., problematic project type of reducing emissions from deforestation),
- **Reduce** risks by project design (e.g., afforestation on abandoned land to prevent leakage),
- **Document** remaining risks transparently (e.g., conservative baseline estimation of historic deforestation rates based on open data), and
- **Mitigate/address** risks and compensate in case of risk materializes (e.g., buffer reserves to compensate for non-permanence).

Transparent information and effective monitoring of LMTs is key for marketing of carbon credits or any ecosystem services. In addition to existing approaches from established schemes in the voluntary carbon market, LMT implementers can benefit from several quality assessment initiatives, including CCQI:

“Es gibt ja mittlerweile auch „Ratingagenturen“, die drei großen sind Calyx (mit der von mir sehr geschätzten Donna Lee), Renooster und Sylvera. Deren Kernaussage: es reicht nicht, sich die Methodiken anzusehen, sondern es geht darum wie einzelne Projekte diese tatsächlich umsetzen.”

Transparency is not only required from credit providers. There is also the need to provide for transparency and clarity to market actors in their search for funding and **safeguarding the coherence of incentive schemes**. This aspect has been addressed by LANDMARC Deliverable 2.5.

Financing opportunities offered by carbon markets **need to consider the specific challenges of LMTs** (non-permanence, leakage, etc.). General assessments at the level of LMTs, as presented in this deliverable, do not guarantee that mitigation results of specific projects can be marketed under certain market mechanisms and individual schemes. Instead, there is the need to consider project design as many risks can only be addressed at the level of concrete project implementation. Assessing environmental integrity risks not only at case study level but also concrete project level will help to:

- ensure LMTs have an overall net-negative effect on GHGs in the atmosphere,
- establish safeguards for implementing LMTs at larger scales,
- provide a differentiated view on (carbon) market opportunities for LMTs,
- improve quality of results and increase attractiveness for financing for LMTs.

Carbon marketing for generating offsets might currently offer the largest market opportunities due to high demand for offsets and a shortage of supply. However, it also bears the risk of taking pressure from necessary fossil fuel emission reductions as current prices for offsets are often way below the costs of mitigation opportunities with the buyers themselves. Moreover, if within a compliance system, fossil fuel emission reduction obligations are compensated with land-use activities more carbon from stable geological reservoirs is being transferred into instable pools in the biosphere that are more easily subject to natural disturbances and other forms of reversals.

The concept of ‘climate responsibility’ can reduce efforts for carbon crediting on the one side and reduce the risk of lowered ambition levels. It could also lead to overall higher carbon prices from which implementers of LMT project could benefit.

Visibility in GHG inventories was discussed to be a requirement for LMT implementation to ensure that activities are effectively contributing to national GHG reduction targets. Shortcomings in GHG inventories still exist leaving certain LMTs in the dark. An example are soil carbon emissions that are underreported in the EU (Bellassen et al. 2022). An increased focus on projects of these LMTs can help gaining momentum for improving GHG inventories. Projects that operate within such blind spots could contribute to improving the NIR GHG monitoring processes by supplying data for differentiating emission factors and support also the development of more advanced methodologies, including providing ground truth data for modelling.

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Annex 1 Protocol

Protocol for assessing environmental integrity and marketability

No.	Criteria	Question	Comment	Answers
1.1	Overview	Definition of LMT type	Specify	Text
1.2		Activities	Specify	Text
1.3		Mitigation type	increasing C removals, reducing emissions, preserving carbon stocks	Select
1.4		Location	Country name	Text
1.5		Geographical scope	field/farm/region/jurisdiction/national	Select
1.6		Carbon pools considered	aboveground biomass/belowground biomass/dead wood/dead organic matter/litter/soil/HWP	Select
1.7		Gases covered	CO ₂ /CO ₂ and non-CO ₂	Select
1.8		Length of activity	number of years	Text
2	Baselines and crediting			
	A baseline represents the level of emissions or removals against which actual emissions or removals are compared to in order to determine the emission reductions or removals resulting from an activity. The term 'baseline' is used to describe both an underlying scenario (e.g., continued deforestation at historical levels) and the associated emissions or removals level (e.g., the emissions resulting from continued deforestation at historical levels). In some instances, baselines are also used for demonstrating additionality. In the land-use sector, standards often consider additionality as automatically demonstrated if the baseline is above the observed emissions under the activity.			
2.1		Do you have information available to establish a baseline?	A baseline is necessary for crediting, e.g., assessing how much carbon has been stored additionally.	Yes, No, Don't know
2.2	If yes	Has a baseline been established?		Yes, No, Don't know
2.3	If yes	Which approach has been used to establish the baseline?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zero baseline (gross-net-accounting) • Historic baseline • Historic adjusted baseline • Projected baseline • Reference area • Other (specify) 	Select
2.4		Method for establishing baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field measurements • Modelling • Statistics • Other (specify) 	Select
2.5		What is the scope of the baseline?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project • Regional • National • International • Other (specify) 	Select
2.6		Do baselines take into account existing (and potential new) policies (e.g. feed-in-tariffs, carbon taxes etc.) as well as mitigation targets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, explain, e.g. reference scenario assumes continuation of current practices 	Yes, No, Don't know
2.7		Has the conservativeness principle been applied?	If yes, explain, e.g. a pool considered is "not a source", conservative baseline	Yes, No, Don't know
3	Additionality			
	Emission reductions or removals are additional if they occur because of the incentives created by carbon credit revenues. Additionality is thus about causality: emission reductions or removals are only additional if they are caused by the			

		incentives from carbon crediting revenues. If they also occurred in the absence of the incentives from the carbon credits, they would not be additional (Schneider 2009. ²¹ ; Gillenwater 2012. ²²). Determining the additionality of an activity is not the same as determining how many emissions reductions or removals result from the implementation of a project (Gillenwater 2012). However, the two issues are related and often considered together, because they determine whether and how carbon credits should be issued.		
3.1		Is the LMT implementation additional?	Meaning: Would the LMT have been implemented without a carbon market opportunity?	Yes, No, Don't know
3.2		Do you have information available to assess additionality?	Additionality assessment requires among others a description of the business as usual/most likely scenario in the absence of a project or carbon market opportunity	Yes, No, Don't know
3.3	If yes	Has additionality been assessed?		Yes, No, Don't know
3.4	If yes		How has additionality been assessed? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic assessment • Legal assessment • Comparison to business as usual • Other (specify) 	Select
4	Non-permanence			
	There is an inherent risk of land use-related mitigation being reversed, as carbon stocks that are preserved or enhanced could be lost through natural or human-induced disturbances at a later point in time. Reversals are associated with carbon pools. The susceptibility of a specific carbon reservoir for reversal depends on the underlying processes how carbon is stored, and in which form it is fixed, as well as the natural and human-induced drivers underlying potential losses at a later stage. Since biomass pools naturally have relatively high turnover rates, carbon from these pools can be released faster than from soil carbon pools.			
4.1		Are there non-permanence risks for the implementation of the LMT?		Yes, No, Don't know
4.2	If yes	What are non-permanence risks for the implementation of the LMT?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of built-up carbon stock due to natural disturbances, e.g. fire, drought, insect outbreaks, change of management practice (increased harvest rates) 	Text
4.3		What is the likelihood of non-permanence?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High • Medium • Low • Don't know 	Select
4.4		Can non-permanence risks be reduced by design of implementation of LMT?		Yes, No, Don't know
4.5	If yes	How?	Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of adapted species • Implementation of LMT only in sufficiently resilient forest types • Strict enforcement of laws 	Text
4.6		Is permanence monitored?		Yes, No, Don't know
4.7	If yes	How is permanence monitored?	e.g. Earth Observation, field measurements.	Text
4.8		For how long is the monitoring of permanence secured?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Text

²¹ Schneider, L. (2009): Assessing the additionality of CDM projects: practical experiences and lessons learned. In: *Climate Policy* (9:3), pp. 242–254. DOI: 10.3763/cpol.2008.0533.

²² Gillenwater, Michael (2012): What is Additionality? GHG Management Institute. Washington D.C. Available at: <https://ghginstitute.org/research/>.

5 Leakage risks				
<p>Activities for reducing emissions or increasing removals in the land-use sector can affect emissions and removals in other sectors or outside the target area. Such displacements can be caused by activities implemented at different scales, including projects, programmes, or jurisdictional approaches. While displacement within the system boundaries is usually reflected in the activity's monitored emissions, leakage is a displacement happening outside the boundaries of the activity (Henders und Ostwald 2012²³).</p> <p>Direct leakage: Leakage effects caused by the direct shift in the supply of products or services from one area to another through the implementation of an activity, such as the displacement of grazing land for cows to another area (activity shifting).</p> <p>Indirect leakage: Leakage effects caused by the implementation of an activity in one area indirectly creating incentives for changes in activities in other areas. Indirect effects are usually caused by the reduction in supply of products or services leading to a shift in markets, such as increased crop production in other areas due to a reduction of crop production on the targeted land area (market effects). Indirect leakage effects can be at local, national and global level.</p> <p>Ecological leakage: Leakage effects caused by the implementation of an activity in one area affecting natural processes stretching out to surrounding ecosystems outside an activity's boundary leading to emissions, e.g., if organic soils in an area are rewetted affecting the hydrological properties of ecosystems outside the area causing tree dieback.</p>				
5.1		Are there leakage risks for the implementation of LMTs?		Yes, No, Don't know
5.2	If yes	What are leakage risks for the implementation of LMTs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct leakage • Indirect local/national leakage (market leakage) • Indirect global leakage (market leakage) • Ecological leakage 	Select
5.3		Can leakage risks be reduced by design of implementation of LMTs?		Yes, No, Don't know
5.4	If yes	How?	<p>Examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of abandoned land for afforestation 	Text
5.5		What other accompanying measures would be needed to reduce the risk of leakage?	<p>Examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy policy • Policies to reduce consumption • Market restrictions 	Text
6 Monitoring				
6.1	<p>The monitoring (measuring, reporting and verification, MRV) required by crediting standards refers to the process of periodically quantifying the emission reductions or removals of an activity. The process involves predefined methods for monitoring, usually specified in baseline and monitoring methodologies and the regular preparation of monitoring reports in which emission reductions or removals are quantified for specific periods. Monitoring reports are usually independently verified.</p> <p>Estimation of emissions and removals for baselines and during the crediting period requires accurate data on carbon stocks and/or stock changes per ha and area information. The first can be provided by methods like, e.g., forest inventories based on field sampling, the latter on statistics and/or remote sensing information. Models can also be used to assess carbon stock changes caused by activities through comparison of alternative scenarios, especially for estimating emissions at larger geographical scales.</p>			
6.2		What indicators are assessed by the MRV system?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon stocks/Carbon stock changes • Area/Area changes • Biodiversity indicators • Other (specify) 	Select
6.3		How are indicators measured?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In situ measurement (National Forest Inventory) • Remote sensing • Modelling • Statistics • Other (specify) 	Select

²³ Henders, S.; Ostwald, M. (2012): Forest Carbon Leakage Quantification Methods and Their Suitability for Assessing Leakage in REDD. In: *Forests* 3 (1), pp. 33–58. DOI: 10.3390/f3010033

6.4		Have uncertainties of emission reduction/removals been estimated?		Yes, No, Don't know
6.5	If yes	How high?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage 	%
6.6		Can uncertainties be reduced by improved monitoring?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	Yes, No, Don't know
6.7	If yes	How?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved temporal resolution Improved spatial resolution (using remote sensing data) Use of additional data Other (specify) 	Select
6.8		Are emissions/removals/carbon stock changes verified for the implementation of LMT?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	No
6.9	If yes	How?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Independent third-party review Certification 	Select/Text
7	Visibility in GHG inventory			
7.1	<p>There needs to be visibility of mitigation measures in national GHG reporting. If LMTs are not reflected in national inventories used to assess compliance in the climate policy framework, effects of these measures cannot be accounted towards national targets. This might have implications for the attractiveness of LMTs in carbon markets as an instrument for national policy making.</p> <p>Nota bene: Questions following are addressing the country rather than the project level. Information to answer the questions can be found in National Determined Contributions (NDC).²⁴ and other national reporting documents to UNFCCC.</p>			
7.2		Is the considered implementation of LMT represented in GHG inventory by separate activity data and emission factors?	Explain, e.g. by differentiating species, management types etc.	Yes, No, Don't know
7.4		Is the land use sector represented in the NDC of the country of implementation of LMT?		Yes, No, Don't know
7.5	If yes	How is the land use sector represented in the NDC of the country of implementation of LMT?	<p>Type of target</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate target Economy-wide target Other (specify) 	Select
7.6			<p>Content of target</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greenhouse gas target Area target Other (specify) 	
7.7			<p>Formulation of target</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Absolute target Relative target (e.g. compared to baseline) Other (specify) 	
8	Double counting			

²⁴ <https://unfccc.int/NDCREG>

8.1	<p>Double counting occurs when a single emission reduction or removal is used more than once towards the achievement of mitigation targets or goals (Fearneough et al. 2020²⁵; Schneider et al. 2019). If occurring on a large scale, double counting has the potential to lead to higher global emissions, ultimately undermining the achievement of climate targets or goals. The Paris Agreement requires Parties to avoid double counting when accounting for NDCs and when using cooperative approaches under Article 6. Avoiding double counting is of special relevance in the context of carbon market mechanisms and if multiple mechanisms operate simultaneously, which is possible under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement. Double counting can occur in three main forms (Prag et al. 2013²⁶; Fearneough et al. 2020; Schneider et al. 2015²⁷): Double issuance of units, double use of units, and double claiming of emission reductions or removals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Double issuance occurs when two units are issued for a single emission reduction or removal. • Double use occurs if an issued unit is used twice by buyers to achieve mitigation pledges. • Double claiming can occur with domestic mitigation targets and with international mitigation targets. 		
8.2		Have credits already been issued for a crediting mechanism or incentive scheme?	Yes, No, Don't know
8.3		Have issued credits already been used by buyers to achieve mitigation pledges?	Yes, No, Don't know
8.4		Will credits be claimed by more than one country (e.g. by a buyer country and the activity host country)?	Yes, No, Don't know
9	Safeguards and co-benefits		
9.1	<p>Safeguards are requirements and procedures of carbon crediting mechanisms aimed at avoiding and reducing their potential negative impacts (Fearneough et al. 2020). Social safeguards relate to human rights, workers' rights, gender issues, rights of indigenous peoples, corruption and economic development, whereas environmental and ecological safeguards, for example, encompass preventing biodiversity loss and maintaining environmental quality (Michaelowa et al. 2019²⁸). Co-benefits refer to positive effects beyond climate change mitigation, that may arise from the implementation of activities under a carbon crediting mechanism, these may be generally related to conserving or promoting ecosystem services and sustainable development goals.</p>		
9.2		Do potential negative direct impacts and risks exist?	Yes, No, Don't know
9.3	If yes	Which?	<p>Examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land tenure issues • Negative impacts on biodiversity • Negative impacts on water • Negative impacts on economy/value chains • Other (specify)
9.4		Can safeguards be put in place to mitigate risks and avoid negative impacts?	Yes, No, Don't know
9.5	If yes	Which?	<p>Examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensation payments to forest owners • Reduction of wood consumption (especially energy wood)

²⁵ Fearneough, H.; Kachi, A.; Mooldijk, S.; Warnecke, C.; Schneider, L. (2020): Future role for voluntary carbon markets in the Paris era, Final report. Umweltbundesamt (ed.), 2020. Online available at: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/5750/publikationen/2020_11_19_cc_44_2020_carbon_markets_paris_era_0.pdf, last accessed on 17 Apr 2021.

²⁶ Prag, A.; Hood, C.; Barata, P. M. (2013): Made to Measure: Options for Emissions Accounting under the UNFCCC (COM/ENVEPOC/IEA/SLT(2013)1). OECD. Paris, 2013. Online available at: <http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=COM/ENV/EPOC/IEA/SLT%282013%291&docLanguage=En>, last accessed on 1 Apr 2022.

²⁷ Schneider, L.; Köllmuss, A.; Lazarus, M. (2015): Addressing the risk of double counting emission reductions under the UNFCCC. In: Climatic Change 131 (4), pp. 473–486. DOI: 10.1007/s10584-015-1398-y.

²⁸ Michaelowa, A.; Shishlov, I.; Hoch, S.; Bofill, P.; Espelage, A. (2019): Overview and comparison of existing carbon crediting schemes. Perspectives, Climate Group GmbH, Freiburg; This work has been commissioned by NEFCO and financed by the Nordic Initiative for Cooperative Approaches (NICA).

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other (specify) 	
9.6		Are co-benefits expected from the implementation of the LMT?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Yes, No, Don't know
9.7	If yes	Which?	<p>Examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased biodiversity • Improved soil quality • Cooling effects through higher biomass stocks • Improved water retention and ground water supply (increased share of broadleaved trees) • Other (specify) 	Text
9.8		How can be ensured that co-benefits can emerge?	<p>Example</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High standards on biodiversity for incentive schemes for private forest owners 	Text

Annex 2 Detailed results of survey

A summary of survey results can be viewed online [here](#). See also separate pdf.